

Conductometric and Gravimetric Study of Barium-Anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic Acid Complex

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Microscopic¹ and photometric² methods have been employed in the estimation of anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic acid in presence of certain other anthraquinone sulphonic acids by counting the number of crystals of barium anthraquinone-1,8 disulphonate. The present investigation deals with the reaction between anthraquinone-1,8 disulphonic acid (Na salt) and barium ions in which a light yellow complex in the ratio of 1:1 is quantitatively precipitated, leaving a clear supernatant liquid after keeping overnight.

FIG. 1. Composition from conductance study of equimolar & non-equimolar solns. by Job's method.

Curve A: $c=1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=1.0$.
 Curve B: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=1.0$.
 Curve C: $c=6.66 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=1.0$.
 Curve D: $c=1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$; $p=0.0$.
 Curve E: $c=4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=2.0$.
 Curve F: $c=3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=2.0$.

FIG. 2. Direct & reverse titrations (monovariation).

Curves A & A₁: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=1$.
 Fixed volume in each=4.0 ml.
 Curves B & B₁: $c=6.66 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=1$.
 Fixed volume in each=4.0 ml.
 Curve C: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=0.5$.
 Fixed volume=3.0 ml metal.
 Curve C₁: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-3}M$; $p=0.5$.
 Fixed volume=6.0 ml reagent.

1. Seaman, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1939, 11, 485.
2. Seaman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1942, 14, 350.
3. Joshi and Jain, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 241.

Barium chloride and anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) used were of B.D.H. AnalaR and chemically pure quality, respectively. The experimental set up was the same as in our previous communication³.

The reaction was studied by the methods of continued variation⁴ [Fig. 1, curves A, B & C (equimolar) and D, E, & F (non-equimolar solutions)] and monovariation⁵ (Fig. 2, curves A, B, & C of direct titration and A₁, B₁, & C₁ of reverse titration) keeping the total volume 12 ml in each case. The plots show the stoichiometry of the complex as 1:1. Here c represents the concentration of the metal solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of the reagent solution).

The precipitation of the light yellow barium complex by this reagent has been found to be quantitative. The precipitation was carried out at the room temperature ($30^{\circ} \pm 1.0^{\circ}$), employing 2% aqueous anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) and an aqueous standard barium chloride solution. The precipitate was filtered in a weighed sintered glass crucible after keeping the contents overnight, washed with distilled water, and dried at 120° . In every case, the precipitate corresponds to the composition $C_{14}H_6O_8S_2Ba$, which indicates that the two sodium atoms present in the reagent molecule are replaced by one barium atom (stoichiometric ratio being 1:1), as shown:

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